

Supporting Information for “Data-driven optimization of seismicity models using diverse data sets: generation, evaluation and ranking using inlabru”

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Introduction The supporting information contains additional text and figures supporting the results presented. These figures and tables were created during the main body of work following the method outlined in the main text.

Text S1: Further information on data types Included below is further information on the different data types used in model construction (Section 3 of main text). The

UCERF3 data used here, from the working group in California earthquake probabilities (WGCEP), is available online at <https://pubs.usgs.gov/of/2013/1165/>.

1. Earthquake point data

The catalogue used in UCERF3 extends back as far as 1769 for the largest magnitude events. The catalogue contains events of $M4$ or greater before 1984 and $M2$ or greater since then. The catalogue is likely complete to $M2$ as far back as 1984, but is certainly not complete to $M4$ before then. The $M5.5$ cut-off was chosen as a magnitude at which clustering would be limited, and includes only 385 events. The computational time for the $M \geq 5.5$ models is such that they run on the order of minutes on a standard desktop. Models including categorical data often take longer to run as a gridded map of the data must be constructed, which we do manually each time. Computation times are not significantly increased by catalogues of up to 50 000 events, but any variable maps that do not cover the entire area of the point data should not be included if possible and will significantly increase computational cost if attempted. Computational time is also largely dependent on the resolution of the mesh used for the model. An example of a mesh constructed for $M5.5+$ events in California, showing the point locations and resulting intensity, is shown in Figure S1.

2. Fault polygons

There are two equally weighted fault models in the UCERF3 logic tree. The differences between these two models are small but potentially significant, offering different descriptions of several fault groups. In keeping with the method used in UCERF3, we apply a 1km buffer to all the fault polygons, and combine this with a second buffer that is dependent on the recorded dip, starting at 0km for dips of 50 degrees and extending to

12km buffers for faults with dips of 90 degrees. We use the combined buffering in the rest of this work, as this provided the best fault model according to this testing. The buffers are shown in Figure S2 while the resulting DIC values for each of the two fault geometries with different buffers applied is shown in Table S1.

2.1. Fault-distance map

The distance from fault map was constructed using the ‘over’ function from the `sp` package (Pebesma & Bivand, 2005; Bivand et al., 2013) to identify which events are within fault polygons. The distance to the closest fault for all off-fault events is then used to construct a map of fault-distance for all points in a grid. This is then included in `inlabru` models as a continuous covariate.

2.2. QFaults

The Quaternary fault model includes faults not included in UCERF3, including many smaller faults to the East of the state and on the California-Nevada boundary. The QFault data does not contain fault dip information for individual faults, so a uniform buffer of 5km has been applied here. This allows us to assess the performance of the UCERF3 fault geometry for describing California seismicity compared to the QFault model.

3. Slip rates

There are four slip rate models used in UCERF3. The first is a geological model based solely on GPS measurements of slip, while the other three models combine geological and geodetic information. The NeoKinema model includes principal stress data modelled with the finite element method of Bird (2009), while the Zeng model (Zeng & Shen, 2016) treats individual faults as buried dislocations within a homogeneous elastic half space,

and models the slip rates accordingly. The averaged block model (ABM) is an average of five different block models used as data within a unified block model inversion. Further details on each of these models is available in Field et al. (2014). Within the framework of UCERF3, the geological model, the NeoKinema model, which has the best fit to GPS data, and the Zeng model, which makes the minimal possible changes to the GPS data, are each given a weighting of 30%, while the ABM model is given only a 10% weighting within the logic tree. The predicted intensities resulting from each of these different slip rate models are shown in Figure S3.

4. Past seismicity

The UCERF3 project makes use of smoothed seismicity for off-fault seismicity probabilities. Within the UCERF3 logic tree, there are branches which make use of the UCERF2 smoothed seismicity based on a Gaussian smoothing over 50km and a new "UCERF3 smoothed seismicity" (Field et al., 2014). The new smoothed seismicity model is described by Felzer (UCERF3 appendix M) and based on the adaptive smoothing method of Helmstetter, Kagan, and Jackson (2007), where the smoothing constant is determined by the distance to the n th earthquake. This means that there will be shorter distance smoothing in areas with many events clustered together and broader smoothing in areas which experience less seismicity. The UCERF3 past seismicity model is derived from all events since 1984 with magnitude ≥ 2.5 . Though different n values are tested, the authors use $n = 8$ to construct the smoothed seismicity model used in UCERF3. Similarly to Werner, Helmstetter, Jackson, and Kagan (2011), they find that a smaller value of n may be more appropriate but results in a map where seismicity is too tightly clustered.

5. Strain rate

While the UCERF3 model makes use of slip rates on individual faults, these slip rate models require an existing detailed fault and geological deformation model, GPS observations and a significant amount of computational modelling. In many areas, fault systems are incompletely mapped and fault slip rate models will simply not exist. The INLA method allows us to identify how well different model components can account for similar spatial patterns of seismicity, and the data available for UCERF3 provides us with a useful starting position from which to add other potentially useful model components.

Figure S4. Model parameter posteriors for best performing $M2.5+$ model

Figure S5. Model component performance across $M2.5+$ and $M5.5+$ models

Figure S6. Input covariates for Ridgecrest example (section 6.3).

Text S2: Comparing adaptively-smoothed and Matérn-smoothed seismicity To properly test the different smoothed seismicity models, we downloaded more recent earthquake information from the ANSS catalogue (<https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/search/>) for the area covering -128° to -113° longitude and 30.5° to 44° latitude, with magnitudes ≥ 2.5 between May 2012 and January 2019. These events are then filtered to include only events within a boundary defined by the locations of the UCERF3 events to restrict the events to the state of California. This includes a total of 6511 events, limited to the same area as the UCERF3 dataset. We tested the performance of the random field only, random field + adaptively smoothed past-seismicity and random field + Matérn smoothed seismicity for events with magnitude ≥ 3.5 . The resulting intensity maps are shown in Figure S7. The Matérn smoothed seismicity has the lowest DIC (7216), followed by the adaptively smoothed seismicity (7295) and the random field only (7354) models. The dif-

ferences in resulting intensity patterns are small, though the edges of the underlying past seismicity models are visible in each of the past seismicity models. The hard boundaries of the UCERF3 gridded past seismicity lead to some visible edge effects on the intensity at the edges of the map which likely contribute to the higher DIC of the adaptively-smoothed model. However we are confident that the Matérn seismicity performs at least as well as the adaptively smoothed seismicity given the similarities in the resulting intensity models.

Figure S8: Removing individual faults

Figure S1. Gaussian random field model with Matérn correlation only for M5.5+ earthquakes in the UCERF3 catalogue. The mesh used to construct the model is also plotted, as are the points representing the events themselves.

Figure S2. Fault polygons from UCERF3 data (top left); as buffered by a uniform 1km buffer only (bottom left); buffered by an amount related to the fault dip only, with a maximum buffer of 12km at 90 degree dip (top right); and combined buffer including both uniform and dip-dependent buffers (bottom right)

Table S1. DIC results for each of the polygon buffer models shown in Figure S1 for both UCERF3 fault geometries (FG). For each buffer a model is constructed with the fault geometry only and for fault geometry + random field. The random field only model for the UCERF *M5.5+* data is also included for reference. Δ DIC compares DIC for the ‘best’ model and δ DIC compares DIC for the next best model

Model	DIC	Δ DIC	δ DIC
Dip Buffer FG1 + random field	5947	0	0
Combined buffer FG1 + random field	5952	5	5
Dip buffer FG2 + random field	5952	5	0
Uniform buffer FG1 + random field	5954	7	2
Combined buffer FG2 + random field	5955	8	1
Uniform buffer FG2 + random field	5959	12	4
Unbuffered FG2 + random field	5963	16	4
Unbuffered FG1 + random field	5964	17	1
Random field only	5967	20	3
Dip buffer FG2	6433	486	466
Combined buffer FG2	6436	486	0
Dip buffer FG1	6437	490	4
Combined buffer FG1	6441	494	4
Uniform buffer FG1	6574	627	133
Uniform buffer FG2	6595	648	21
Unbuffered FG1	6676	729	81
Unbuffered FG2	6683	736	7

Figure S3. Predicted intensities for the four slip models in the UCERF3 model. The left column shows intensities for models that include fault slip rates only. The middle column shows intensities for models with slip rates and random fields, and the third column shows how each of these models is different from a random field only model.

Figure S4. Model parameter posteriors for the top model for M2.5+ seismicity, determined by DIC. This model includes (clockwise from top left) the past seismicity, strain rate, fault distance and slip rate parameters.

Component	Performance		Availability	Alternatives
	Individually	In combination		
<p>Past seismicity</p>	Best of tested components	Always improves models when added	Can be constructed for any catalogue	Existing past seismicity models
<p>GEM strain rate</p>	Performs well	Improves models when added	Global model	Slip rates on individual faults
<p>UCERF fault geometry</p>	Performs less well	Explains some spatial structure, improves combination models	Not always available	Fault distance may be more useful in areas with more uncertain fault maps
<p>Fault distance map</p>	Performs poorly	Improves other models when added - may be more useful in areas with more uncertain fault geometry	Can be constructed if fault map available	Fault geometry
<p>Fault slip rates</p>	Variable performance with dataset	Sometimes useful in combination models	Not always available	Strain rate

Figure S5. Input model components and their contribution to models of spatially varying seismicity. The individual performance column describes the performance of a model with the component and a random field only, while the combined performance considers the way in which the component contributes to different models (see Table 3).

Figure S6. Input covariates for the Ridgecrest sequence, with events shown in red. Clockwise from top: UCERF fault geometry, strain rate, past seismicity and Quaternary fault model.

Figure S7. Models for M3.5+ past seismicity from 2012-2019 using (left) random field only, (middle) random field + adaptively smoothed past seismicity and (right) random field + Matérn smoothed past seismicity.

Figure S8. Δ DIC values for models where each fault is removed with (black) and without (red) random field components, compared with slip rate (top left) and fault area (top right). Differences in Δ DIC when the random field is or is not included (bottom left) and slip rate compared with fault area (bottom right). The models with random field (black) generally have higher Δ DIC than the models without the random field (red) where the Δ DIC is small. The effect on DIC of removing faults is not particularly well correlated with fault area or slip rate. This is likely because neither of these factors are good predictors of whether an event with $M \geq 5.5$ will occur within the fault polygon. The biggest positive changes in DIC appear to be for faults with a reasonably high slip rate (≥ 10 mm/yr), but high slip-rate faults are also associated with larger negative changes in DIC, because the factor which most affects the DIC value of a fault is the number of events that occur on it.

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